

Assessment of TETFund Intervention on Research and Staff Development in Tertiary Institutions in Katsina State, Nigeria

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APA citation: Saadu, H., Danjuma, M., Umar, B.D., & Dahiru, S.Y.(2025). Assessment of TETFund Intervention on Research and Staff Development in Tertiary Institutions in Katsina State, Nigeria. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 5(3), 187-191

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 21 Oct 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Staff training, research, publication, instructional materials and equipment</p>	<p>The study assessed TETFund intervention on research and staff development in tertiary institution in Katsina state. The descriptive survey research was designed. Using random sampling technique; 346 of teaching and non-teaching staff were sampled from the population of 3793 of five public tertiary institutions. A self-design questionnaire was used for data collection, the questionnaire items were rated using a five-point likert rating scale. The data obtained was analyzed using ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The major finding revealed 3.62 average mean score indicated general agreement on the TETFund intervention 3.51 average mean score signifying staff agreement on the TETFund intervention in the area of research, book development and publication. However, the result revealed 3.11 average mean score for TETFUND intervention in the area of science and science education in the tertiary institutions. The findings also revealed no significant difference among respondents on TETFund intervention in the area of research, book development and publication, provision of instructional materials, equipment and staff training and development in the tertiary institution as well as in the area of science and science education. Some recommendations proffered; TETFund should allocate more funds in the area of science and science education in tertiary institutions. Moreover, to promote better working environment of the educational institutions TETFund should improve staff training and development as well as enhancing research funding, book development and publication.</p>

1. Introduction

Early Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) is an intervention agency set up by the federal government of Nigeria to provide supplementary support to all levels of public tertiary institutions of learning with the main objective of using funds alongside project management for the rehabilitation, restoration and consolidation of tertiary education in Nigeria. The funds are disbursed for the general improvement of education in federal and state tertiary education (TETFund, 2018). TETFund was established by an Act of No. 16 of 2011. The act replaced the Education Tax fund Act Cap. E4 Laws of the federation of Nigeria 2004 and education tax fund (Amendment) Act No 17, 2003 (TETFund, 2017). The Agency was set up to administer and disburse education Tax collected to the public tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria which was defined under the Act as universities, polytechnics and colleges of education. According to TETFund (2017), the main source of income available to the TETFund is "the 2% education tax paid the assessable profit of companies registered in Nigeria". The tax is collected by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The goals of TETFund include among others the 1) Provision of essential physical infrastructure for teaching and learning, 2) Provision of instructional materials and equipment, 3) Research book development and publication (journals and books), 4) Academic staff training and development, and 5) Any other need which in the opinion of the board of trustees is considered critical and essential for the improvement of quality and maintenance of standards in the educational institutions (Amini & Wapmuk, 2018; Osobe. & Mukoro, 2024).

The board of trustees (BOT) of the TETFund is statutorily charged with the responsibility of administering, managing and disbursing these funds to beneficiaries in the public tertiary educational institutions under established guidelines so as to achieve the aforementioned goals. The beneficiaries of the agency are required to submit project proposals upon which the fund would be applied. TETFund requires that such projects must be in line with the beneficiary institution's core mandate and should be relevant to teaching, learning and research; including improvement of the learning and teaching environment.

As approved by the board of trustees, TETFund interventions can be categorized as 1) Regular annual intervention: this comprises infrastructural and equipment/furniture-based intervention projects, equipment fabrication, ICT support, library intervention, academic staff training and development, research, publication, conference attendance, manuscript development, teaching practice and TETFund project maintenance. 2) Special intervention: this comprises high impact intervention and BOT special intervention. The regular intervention is yearly for all beneficiary institutions of TETFund. The special intervention usually is at the discretion of the BOT, on equality of geo-political zones as enshrined in the enabling Act.

Ajiboye & Musa (2014) stated that, training in an organization is a way of achieving the goals and objectives of the organization. Organization finds it very easy to meet up to its target with highly trained workforce. It is capable of achieving its main objective at a shortage possible time period hence training and developing an employee in an organization is a source of being where the organization wants to be. It is also a measure of performance of employee in the organization and also a measure of the organizational performance in the same industry. Training and development is a planned effort by an organization to facilitate learning of job behavior. Training implies teaching lower level or teaching employees how to do their present jobs, while development is teaching professionals the skills needed for both present and future jobs. Based on the foregoing, it is an indication that the importance of research and staff training and development cannot be over emphasized in tertiary institutions of learning. In view of that availability and adequacy of funds are very useful for the provision of educational resources for effective and efficient teaching and learning in the tertiary institutions of learning.

1.1 Statement of the problems

The effectiveness of any institution depends to a great extent on the quality and adequacy of educational resources. However, effective and efficient services in the institutions of learning cannot be operated and

RESEARCH ARTICLE

sustained without adequate funds. Therefore, before the commission of TETFund, Nigeria tertiary institutions of learning were facing serious challenges in terms of teaching and staff training and development which hindered effectiveness and efficiency in the institutions. There were also poor research fund, book development and publication; and poor staff training and development. This was supported by Chidere (2016) who revealed that people complain about teaching materials, as well as poor staff development and researches in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Chidere (2016) opined that there is decay in human and materials in Nigerian tertiary institutions as a result of these, Federal government of Nigeria established TETFund as an intervention agency and charged with responsibility of administering, managing and disbursing funds to beneficiaries in the public tertiary educational institutions. The main source of funds available to the TETFund is the 2% education tax paid from the assessable profit of companies registered in Nigeria. The funds were mainly used to address the challenges facing the institutions. Therefore, this research study intended to assess the performance of TETFund in achieving the solutions to the challenges facing the tertiary institutions in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Azubuikwe, Ogbodo & Ezejiogor (2017) opined that inadequate funding of tertiary institutions has had adverse effects on teaching and research. The effect of inadequate funding is evident in the fact that the physical facilities in respective tertiary institutions are in the state of disrepair, several capital and research projects have been abandoned, laboratories and libraries are ill equipped, academic staff do not attend conferences regularly (Azubuikwe et al., 2017).

Thus, the study was set to achieve the following objectives to; 1) Ascertain the TETFund intervention in the area of research, book development and publication (journals and books) in tertiary institutions in Katsina state. 2) Investigate the TETFund intervention in the provision of staff training and development in tertiary institutions in Katsina state. 3) Determine the contributions of TETFund intervention on the area of science and science education in tertiary institutions in Katsina state, 2015 to 2025.

1.2 Research Hypotheses

Null hypotheses were formulated:

1. HO₁. There is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on TETFund interventions in the provision of instructional materials and equipment among tertiary institutions in Katsina state.
2. HO₂. There is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on TETFund interventions in the provision of research, book development and publication among tertiary institutions in Katsina state.
3. HO₃. There are no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on TETFund interventions in the provision of staff training and development among tertiary institutions in Katsina state.

1.3 Significance of the study

The outcome of this study will hopefully benefit staff, students, tertiary institutions awarding degree in Katsina state; TETFund, National Universities Commission (NUC), National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), National Polytechnics Commission (NPC), other researchers, government, text book publishers and other organizations in the following ways:

It will give an insight to both teaching and non-teaching staff in tertiary institutions in Katsina state about the nature, type, and level, mode of access and benefit of access to TETFund intervention. It will create information to supervisory bodies such as NUC as degree awarding institutions on whether or not the TETFund intervention yield any significant impact on research and staff development with a view to reviewing, monitoring or improving the intervention. It will serve as an important source of literature to other fellow researchers who may wish to conduct a similar study in the area.

The outcome of this study may benefit government with a view of sensitizing the rate at which TETFund intervention programs contributed towards the development of tertiary institutions in Katsina state. Text book publishers will find the outcome of this study very useful in producing text books that may create awareness to staff, students and the entire community on the nature, types, level and impact of TETFund intervention with a view to appreciating improvement or otherwise.

Professional organizations like Nigerian association of educational administrators and planners (NAEAP), Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN), Botanical Society of Nigeria (BOSON), Zoological Society of Nigeria (ZOSON) and many others may use the outcome of this study in

organizing developmental programmes such as conference, seminars/symposium and workshop with a view to sensitizing members of academia on access, utilization and impact of TETFUND intervention.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Research design

The descriptive survey research design was adopted by asking set of questions prepared in the form of questionnaire. Questionnaires were used since it involved large number of individuals (Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun, 2015). The most common types of instruments used in descriptive survey research are the questionnaire and interview schedule (Fraenkel et al., 2015). Obadan (2012) opined that to be able to generalize from the sample of the population, the sample has to be representative of the population.

2.2 Population of the study

The population of the study comprised all the staff of both teaching and non-teaching in public tertiary institutions in Katsina state. The population of the study comprised three thousand seven hundred and ninety-three staff (3793). Out of which one thousand eight hundred and ninety-five (1895) teaching staff and one thousand eight hundred and ninety-eight (1898) non-teaching staff as indicated in the distribution of the table 1.

Table 1 Staff population from the institutions

S/N Name of institutions	Population of teaching of staff	Population of non-teaching staff	Total
1. Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina	550	496	1046
2. Federal University Dustin-ma, Katsina	494	623	1117
3. Federal College of Education, Katsina	350	227	577
4. Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsin-ma	230	172	402
5. Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic	371	280	651
Total	1895	1898	3793

Source: Management of the Institutions concerned (2018-2019).

2.3 Sample and sampling techniques

Three hundred and forty-six (346) staffs were selected as sample size from the total population; three thousand seven hundred and ninety three (3793) of both teaching and non-teaching staff (Researcher advisor, 2006). The sample size was then proportionately distributed among the institutions concerned as show in the table 2.

Table 2 sample size drawn from research population

Institution	Sample of teaching staff	Sample of non-teaching staff	Total
1. Umaru Musa Yar'adua university, Katsina	50	45	95
2. Federal University Dutsin-ma Katsina	56	46	102
3. Federal College of Education Katsina	37	17	54
4. Isa Kaita College of Education Dutsin-ma	21	16	37
5. Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic	34	24	58
Total	192	148	346

Therefore, proportionate random sampling technique (Fraenkel, et al., 2015) was adopted to select one hundred and ninety-two (192) from teaching and one hundred and forty-eight (148) non-teaching staff from the entire population.

2.4 Instrumentations

The questionnaire modified from (Ochuu, 2015) was used for TETFund intervention on staff research and development was used for data collection. The questionnaire was a closed-ended type so as to provide control over the participants' range of response alternatives. It is consisted of five sections, section A-D. Section A contained the bio-data which

RESEARCH ARTICLE

comprised of four items and sections B-D, the main questionnaire comprised of three sections as follows:

Section B ascertained the contributions of TETFund intervention programme in the provision of research, book development and publication in tertiary institutions in Katsina state. Section C investigated the contributions of TETFund intervention in the provision of staff training and development in tertiary institutions in Katsina state. Section D assessed the contributions of TETFund intervention on the area of science and science education in Katsina state, 2015 to 2025.

The questionnaire items was rated using a five points Likert scale rating as; strongly agreed (5), agreed (4), undecided (3), disagreed (2) and strongly disagreed (1) for section B-D. By using these sets of response options, indicated their degree of agreement or disagreement with the statements. The scoring made was coded using 5,4,3,2, and 1 as shown above respectively in order to rank the relative relevance of the variables.

2.5 Validity of the instrument

Face and content validities of the instrument was ensured by giving the questionnaire to statisticians and other experts in the field of educations, and English language and their comments was taken into consideration in designing the final questionnaire. So as to determine the appropriateness, correctness, meaningfulness and usefulness of the specific inferences researchers make based on the data collected (Fraenkel, et al., 2015).

2.6 Pilot study

The main aim of pilot study is to determine the feasibility of the methodology adopted for the study. According to Fraenkel et al (2015) the purpose of pilot study is to detect any problems so that they can be remedied before the proper study is carried out. Simple random sampling technique was adopted in choosing the institution for pilot testing for this research work. The pilot study was conducted at Federal College of Education (technical) Bichi Kano state, in order to test the reliability of the instrument. A pilot sample of thirty-six (36) staff was used, 18 each to teaching and non-teaching staff.

2.7 Reliability of the instrument:

Split-half method was adopted to establish the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered once. The scores obtained were systematically splitted into two using odd and even numbers. The two set of scores was then correlated using spearman rank order correlation technique. The reliability of half instrument was obtained. The value was then substituted into spearman's Brown formula, and a reliability coefficient of 0.92 was obtained. Thus, indicated high reliability of the instrument.

2.8 Procedure for data collection

The introductory letters endorsed by the researcher's-based institution was used to seek permission from the administrators of the educational institutions concerned for data collection. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and adequate time was given for the staff to fill the questionnaire. The filled questionnaires from the staff were collected for data analysis.

2.9 Statistical Analysis

Table 3: Frequencies, means of respondents on each statement on the contribution of TETFund intervention in the area of research, book development and publication in tertiary institution in Katsina State 2015 to 2025. Using five Likert scale rating; Strongly Agreed = SA; Agreed = A; Undecided = U; Disagreed = D; Strongly = SD. The two category of respondents; Teaching staff = TS or Non-teaching staff = NS. While, N = Number of the respondents.

TETFund intervention on the provision of research, book development and publication in tertiary institutions in Katsina state.	Category of respondents	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	Mean
1 TETFund gives fund for the conduct of research for teaching and learning in your institutions.	TS	81	99	8	8	1	197	4.27
	NS	56	67	18	8	0	149	4.15
2 Academic staffs are now conducting regular research as a result of fund provided by TETFund.	TS	62	88	15	31	1	197	3.91
	NS	54	41	29	25	0	149	3.83
3 TETFund encourages group research in your institution.	TS	51	85	34	24	3	197	3.80
	NS	42	44	45	15	3	149	3.72
4 Academic staff received fund provided by TETFund for manuscript development in the institution.	TS	47	102	17	27	4	197	3.77
	NS	37	52	44	16	0	149	3.74

The data obtained was processed using statistical packages; PAST 3 (PALEontological STATistics version 3.25) and (SPSS version 23). The descriptive statistics of frequencies, simple percentages, means and standard deviations was used to analyze and construct bar-charts of the number of respondents of each statement items on the contribution of TETFund interventions. While inferential statistic through the use of ANOVA to test the Null hypotheses of the research at 0.05 level of significance.

3. Results

Figure 1: Number of the respondents

Figure 1: Showed that 197 (56%) and 149 (44%) questionnaires were dispatched from both teaching and non-teaching staff respectively. Thus, three hundred forty six (346) questionnaires, representing 100% were filled and retrieved.

Figure 2: Demographic information of the respondents

Figure 2 showed educational qualifications; Bachelors/HND is predominant educational qualifications of the staff from FUDMA and FCE with 44%, and 43% respectively. This is followed by Masters educational qualifications of which staff from UMYU with 35% and FUDMA having 33%. NCE/ND is the least educational qualifications having 7 to 13%. Furthermore, on the years of working experience the result showed 16 and above years to have the highest frequencies with 48% and 40% from FCE and HUKP respectively. The least is staff with working experience 11 to 15 years having 16% to 28%.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

5	Some books and journals in the institution were published as a result of TETFund intervention.	TS	47	102	32	14	2	197	3.90
		NS	38	64	35	11	1	149	3.85
6	I have contributed some parts chapters in the book or journal published from TETFund intervention.	TS	30	62	8	65	32	197	2.96
		NS	9	4	2	71	63	149	1.83
7	TETFund gives special incentives to academic staff before or after research, book development and/or publication in the institution.	TS	25	68	45	56	3	197	3.28
		NS	32	45	50	21	1	149	3.58
8	TETFund assisted in the provision of adequate funds for research, book development and/or publication of journals and books in your institution.	TS	37	78	34	44	4	197	3.51
		NS	33	56	28	26	6	149	3.56
Total/Average score		Both	251	479	234	308	112	2768	3.62

Table 3 above revealed that TETFund intervention contributed in the area of research, book development and publication in tertiary institutions in Katsina state. Items 1 to 5 and 8 have the mean scores of ≥ 3.51 for both teaching staff and non-teaching staff which indicated agreement that TETFund intervention contributed in the area in question. Whereas, items 6 to 7 showed ≥ 3.28 signifying staffs' disagreement of TETFund intervention in said area. However, on item 7 only non-teaching staff agreed on the TETFund intervention in question. Similarly, the average mean score showed 3.62 indicating general agreement on the TETFund intervention.

The respondents' opinion was corroborated with other finding where library facilities cum books and journal were procured through TETFund intervention (Fejoh & Adesanwo, 2021). One billion, nine million two hundred and seventy three three hundred and eighty three Naira only (₦1,009,273,383) was spent from January 2021 to date for academic manuscript into books intervention. Similarly, twelve billion, eighty-four million Naira only (₦12,084,000,000) was amount approved for library development intervention (TETFund intervention, 2025).

Table 4: Frequencies, means of respondents on each statement on the contribution of TETFund intervention in the area of staff training and development in tertiary institutions in Katsina State, 2015 to 2025.

TETFund intervention on staff training and development in tertiary institutions in Katsina state		Category of respondents	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	Mean
1	Trained staffs are now sufficient as a result of TETFund intervention.	TS	54	98	25	15	5	197	3.92
		NS	55	71	8	13	2	149	4.10
2	TETFund contributed in the area of international training and retraining of staff in your educational institution.	TS	44	71	9	67	6	197	3.41
		NS	32	24	46	44	3	149	3.26
3	Many staff in your institution have enjoyed national training and retraining sponsored by TETFund.	TS	87	89	4	15	2	197	4.24
		NS	45	75	15	12	2	149	4.00
4	Staffs are now attending national conferences or workshops supported by TETFund.	TS	99	84	4	9	1	197	4.38
		NS	57	76	7	8	1	149	4.21
5	Staffs are sent to international conferences as a result of TETFund intervention.	TS	12	88	4	89	4	197	3.08
		NS	23	41	0	76	9	149	2.95
6	Sufficient funds were given to staff for national and international training and retraining in the institution.	TS	36	30	5	78	48	197	2.63
		NS	29	52	11	49	8	149	3.30
7	Adequate funds were given to staff for national and international conference in the institution.	TS	31	23	21	83	47	205	2.65
		NS	1	7	41	42	58	149	2.00
8	Have you ever benefited with staff development programme such as training, retraining, seminars, workshops and conference attendance provided by TETFund.	TS	70	89	6	15	17	197	3.91
		NS	59	69	2	11	8	149	4.07
Total/Average score		Both	261	399	90	443	199	2776	3.51

Table 4 revealed that TETFund intervention on staff training and development in tertiary institutions in Katsina State. For instance, items 1, 3 to 4 and 8 recorded mean scores of ≥ 3.91 which indicated that both teaching and non-teaching staff have agreed that TETFund intervention on staff training and development. On the other hand, items 2 and 5 to 7 recorded ≤ 3.30 mean scores indicating disagreement in those intervention areas. However, the average mean score showed 3.51 denoting general

staff agreement on the said intervention. This result is in line with previous finding that TETFund intervene in the area of research and training of staff (Fejoh & Adesanwo, 2021). Additionally, it supported the fact that one billion, nine hundred and eighty-one million fifty four nine hundred and seventy eight Naira sixty kobo only (₦1,981,054,978.60) for academic research journal intervention from January 2021 to date (TETFund intervention, 2025).

Table 5: Frequencies, means of respondents of each statement item on intervention on the area of science and science education in tertiary institutions in Katsina State 2015 to 2025.

TETFund intervention on the area of Science and Science education in Katsina state.		Category of respondents	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	Mean
1	On staff training and development in tertiary institutions, more emphasis is being place in the area of science and science education.	TS	55	88	7	15	32	197	3.60
		NS	30	45	48	14	12	149	3.45
2	On number sponsorship for staff workshop/conferences in tertiary institutions, more emphasis is being place in the area of science and science education.	TS	15	22	9	67	84	197	2.07
		NS	5	9	42	49	44	149	2.21
3	On funding for staff manuscript to textbook development in	TS	71	89	8	22	7	197	3.99

RESEARCH ARTICLE

	tertiary institutions more emphasis is being place in the area of science and science education.	NS	45	75	15	12	2	149	4.00
4	The provision of research and journal publication in tertiary institutions there more emphasis to the area of science and science education.	TS	33	24	5	98	37	197	2.58
		NS	36	12	24	76	1	149	3.04
	Total/Average score	Both	290	364	158	353	219	1384	3.11

Table 5 Showed TETFund intervention contributed on intervention on the area of science and science education in tertiary institutions in Katsina State, where the result revealed items 3 having 3.99 and 4.00 for both teaching staff and non-teaching staff. However, in item 1 only teaching agreed with 3.6 mean scores while non-teaching staff have 3.45 mean score indicating disagreement about the TETFUND intervention in the said area.

On the contrary, in items 2, 4 as well as average mean score revealed ≤ 3.11 mean scores.

5. Testing of Null hypotheses

There is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on three TETFund interventions among tertiary institutions in Katsina state. ANOVA was used to test the Null hypotheses as showed in Table 6.

Table 6: Summary of ANOVA on the various TETFund interventions

Variables	N	Mean	df	F	Sig
H ₁ : TETFund interventions in the area of research, book development and publication	346	39.40	15	0.261	0.617
H ₂ : TETFund interventions in the provision of instructional Materials, equipment and staff training and development	346	34.70	15	0.013	0.911
H ₃ : TETFund interventions in the area of science and science education	346	34.60	15	0.039	0.850

Table 6 above showed that the 346 responses on each variable of TETFund intervention; the TETFund interventions of research book development and publication having a highest mean of 39.40 and $F(0.261) p > 0.05$, followed by the TETFund interventions in the provision of instructional materials and equipment staff training and development with a mean of 39.40 and $F(0.013) p > 0.05$ and the least is the TETFund interventions in the area of science and science education with a mean of 39.40 and $F(0.039) p > 0.05$. However, all the Null hypotheses are accepted. Thus, indicating no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on the three TETFund interventions among tertiary institutions in Katsina state.

6. Conclusion

This paper investigated the assessment of TETFund interventions in tertiary institution in Katsina state, Nigeria. Based on the results of the research the TETFund intervened in the area of research, book development and publication. Others include the provision of instructional materials, equipment and staff training and development. The interventions could go a long way in boosting the moral of staff of Nigerian tertiary institution. However, TETFund interventions only complement governments' effort in educational sectors. Education being backbone of national development, the government across all levels should not relent their effort toward vigorous investment in the area.

7. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the research findings;

1. To boosts, scientific and technological developments, there is need for TETFund to allocate more funds in the area of science and science education in tertiary institutions.
2. TETFund should give more emphasis in the area of staff development particularly for the research and training of academic staff.
3. Considering the positive impact of TETFund in tertiary institutions, state government should also step up similar bodies to supplement TETFund efforts of ensuring adequate funded of tertiary institutions in the country.

Funding sources:

Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) Abuja Nigeria under the Institutional Based Research Grant (IBR)

Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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